

ENHANCED VEHICULAR CLOUD FRAMEWORK FOR REAL-TIME TRACKING AND MANAGEMENT IN SMART TRANSPORTATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract

“The development of vehicular cloud computing holds the potential to revolutionize intelligent transportation systems in smart cities. Major applications include accident reporting/prevention, parking services, and traffic tracking. This paper proposes an intelligent public transportation system leveraging vehicular cloud technology. Unlike existing systems reliant on GPS for vehicle tracking, our approach employs Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) devices to access vehicle locations. We present a smart transportation system integrating DSRC and vehicular cloud, designed to offer users real-time availability and running information about vehicles. Experimental results demonstrate that our proposed model, utilizing DSRC for tracking, yields more accurate outcomes compared to traditional GPS-based methods. The system architecture comprises vehicles, stations, sensors, roadside units (RSUs), cloud storage, and display services, facilitating efficient communication, data storage, and retrieval. This study not only advances the state-of-the-art in vehicular cloud computing but also presents a practical solution for enhancing smart transportation systems.

Index Terms: Vehicular Cloud, DSRC, Public Transportation System, Smart City, Vehicle Tracking.

1. INTRODUCTION

Latterly lot of urban areas are converted into smart cities by implementing and improving Information communication Technologies, not only the urban areas but also the rural areas are becoming smart nowadays. Already certain urban cities have been developed as smart cities and others are being developed. Smart cities are developed in almost all the fields like smart healthcare, smart transportation, smart grid, smart home, smart hospitals, smart tourism etc. When the above fields are achieved, it lead the way to smart city development [23]. Among this the public transportation is most important feature which affects the public quality of life. Smart transportation system offers different modes of services to develop the city. To improve and manage the quality of citizens life, government is preparing lot of plans for public transport in smart city. Some of the plans like creating a system which can inform in real-time the timing of public vehicles in each station, a system of intelligent traffic management, a system of intelligent parking, intelligent traffic light etc. From which the challenging plan is information of public vehicles in each station [11].

Vast amount of research taken place on the above challenge based on smart public transportation system [17]. Mostly to identify the information of current location about the nearest vehicles to the stations, GPS (global positioning system) combined with GSM (global system for mobile) or GPRS (general packet radio service) were implemented. In this combination, the GPS is used to locate the vehicles which arrives to the station and GSM/GPRS is to provide information to the user based on their request. So that the user can avoid can be stored in the cloud to access it remotely. We use DSRC since it is a very short-range communication system comparing to the GPS. To access GPS, we need to access it through the GPS satellite and signals may be blocked at times. But DSRC can be accessed within a short distance. Nowadays there are many systems implemented to track the location of trains like which is used in real time. When we use DSRC device there is a possibility for updating the information automatically. GPS uses high level data communication. There are possibilities of time delay as well. So, this article focuses to overcome all this by implementing public transportation system using DSRC communication device.

This manuscript is organized as follows: In Section II, we present an overview of vehicular cloud in smart city. In Section III, we present the hybrid transportation tracking system. In Section IV, we present the results and discussion. In Section V, we present the experimental challenges on the system. Lastly the paper is concluded with future work in Section VI.

2. VEHICULAR CLOUD IN SMART CITY

A vehicular cloud computing includes a collection of vehicles with the network access to share, compute and store the unlimited data through internet. VCC is a developing technology used to access the resources on demand and provide services to run their application in vehicles [29]. Nowadays big urban cities are slowly developing into smart cities. In smart cities, intelligent transportation systems (ITS) are playing a vital role. ITS is planned to restructure the transport systems like vehicle operation, traffic management and pass information to the drivers for safety [20]. Intelligent transportation system is implemented to achieve traffic efficiency, energy conservation and improve safety to drivers and users with communication and information technologies. Communication and operations of any transportation medium like air travel, roadways, ocean waterways and rail transportation are covered by ITS [24]. In ITS vehicles have to assemble data, spread and infer through a wide range of sensors and other resources used in IoT, smart transport systems etc. Here in ITS data are collected and scattered through a communication infrastructure and disappear as they drive into the physical objects. So along with different types of services provided in ITS, storage of information and enabling heterogeneous communication between vehicles. Many research where taking place to provide different types of services with mechanisms for storage and establish communication between devices. To communicate, monitor, store and manage the stored data Vehicular cloud computing is implemented with intelligent transportation system these days in smart cities [20].

A. Smart City

A smart city is defend-able and innovative which ex- changes information between its own different subsystems using ICT *Information and Communication Technologies* and also other communication methods. In smart city this exchange of information observes and merge censorious conditions of all the subsystem including railways, roadways, airways, water ways, seaports, home, buildings, tunnels, bridges, etc. and use its communication resources in an efficient way. And also monitor and maintain the security while increasing the services in the city based on IT, Social and business connections. An illustration of a smart city model is given Figure 1.

Fig 1: An illustration of smart city

As smart city is becoming smarter day by day, everything is becoming smart like smart home, smart meters, intelligent transportation system, smart water, smart health care, smart food, smart education, smart business etc. Among this the most important research is based on public transportation system. The main issue in the public transportation is lack of information about the routes and the vehicle to the public or customer and other vehicles. Intelligent smart transportation systems are implemented to provide the real time transportation information systems for the commuter. So that the commuter will be able to plan for better traveling with low waiting time and also can find out the alternate solutions to reach destination faster [15].

Implementing smart transportation system many research is being done like to reduce crowd in metro station, giving information about the vehicles to the travelers, maintaining traffic congestion, controlling traffic light etc. We focus on the public transportation system were to the real time information about the public vehicles to the users. So that users utilize this facility to reach their destination soon and take alternate solutions as per their requirements [2].

B. Vehicular Cloud

Nowadays modern vehicles are equipped with different resources like storage, computing, information passing and internet for decision making. These resources allow to benefit various services. Here resources are kept idle for long time in some areas. In this case some of the resources are not utilized by the other vehicles which are in need.

Hence to reduce and utilize the resources properly vehicular cloud is introduced [18] [16]. Vehicular cloud computing can be defined as “a collection of independent vehicles in which computing, storage, communication, sensing and physical resources are coordinated and dynamically allocated to the users” [29].

A VCC brings the versatile cloud into another system with vehicles and it is named as vehicular cloud. This system offers access of boundless computing, putting away, and information assets through web to process, store, download and transfer [16]. The amalgamation of cloud and VANET is Vehicular cloud System [1]. In VANET still there are underutilized re- sources, requirements and services are additionally slacking. To meet these prerequisites and services of VANET application the co-activity between vehicles is presented through cloud arrange as appeared in the Figure 2. A VCC is another rising innovation which is utilized by customers to get to the assets on interest and run their application in the vehicles and give services. The Vehicular cloud computing has a high power over traffic and management, road security by legitimately utilizing assets like computing, storage, and web [18].

Fig 2: Vehicular Cloud

Vehicular cloud computing is developed to utilize the underutilized resources of vehicular ad-hoc network efficiently. Each vehicle in the cloud can be considered as the cloud node with in the neighborhood vehicles. Vehicular cloud computing is classified based on the services it provides, application, cloud organization and layers [9].

The vehicular cloud comprises of three layers like cloud as an infrastructure, cloud as a platform and cloud as a service. The cloud infrastructure layer gives storage, computation, communication through internet to vehicular cloud computing. In vehicular distributed computing the cloud administration offers services like network as a service, cooperation as a service and storage as a service are introduced as Service Types in the given Figure 3.

Network as a service gives the correspondence between neighbor vehicles through web. Storage as a service can offer additional capacity to vehicles. Cooperation as a service gives administrations to drivers by means of V2V correspondence. The association of vehicular cloud computing is shaped as static when vehicles stay static in shopping centers or parking structures. For instance, consider an organization that offers Data Innovation administrations and answers for its clients. In such organizations numerous vehicles of employers and employees stay inactive in the parking garage and their computational assets additionally remain un-utilized. Also, Dynamic vehicular cloud when vehicles are wandering with high portability and the system changes instantly, the versatility parameter assume a critical job in VC development to achieve this nowadays smart cities are included with vehicular cloud [29] [9].

Fig 3: Service Types

Smart city or digital city is an intelligent environment which creates communication technologies to pass on information and create an interactive atmosphere. Preferably we talk about vehicles, Vehicles in the smart city can communicate, collect, transmit, interpret information among vehicles and other infrastructure through sensors, cameras and other communication resources etc. [27]. Apart from all these communication and transportation services, in smart transportation system to increase the computational resources and communication, storage and management services are created using vehicular cloud. The collection of vehicles in the smart transportation need to pass on the information between vehicles and to the infrastructure. This communication is possible in the smart city but to manage the storage and interactive mechanisms central vehicular cloud services are implemented [20]. Infrastructure installed on the road side like Road side Units are the part of the vehicular cloud, they rent the resources and also collect information to send and store it in the cloud as shown in the Figure 4. [3]. So that the communication is made among vehicles, infrastructure and a cloud network.

Fig 4: Vehicular Cloud Communication

Vehicular cloud in the smart city is designed to provide different types of services like storage, network, information, computing and entertainment as a service. These services are provided with storage of information and communication resources via RSU to the central vehicular cloud in both static and dynamic environment of vehicles in smart transportation. Integrating the Road Side Units in the vehicular cloud environment improves all the management services. Mostly vehicular cloud in smart city transportation system is applicable in parking lots, traffic management, public safety etc as shown in the Figure 5 [24].

Fig 5: Vehicular Cloud Communication in Smart City

C. Vehicle-to-Infrastructure Communication

The forte of vehicular to infrastructure is that the communication model where it can specifically impart the information to the component in the Road side unit (RSU). Also, communication is done between infrastructure to vehicular. The components on the

roadside incorporate RFID, camera, streetlights, Roadside, stopping, traffic lights [29]. Here the correspondence is bidirectional and remote which is appeared in Figure 6. V to I utilizes DSRC (Dedicated short-range correspondence) frequencies to exchange the information. From framework the segments are exchanged through ad-hoc systems. V2I communication can be utilized for a wide range of road and vehicles. By actualizing calculations information trade among vehicles and foundation parts are finished. This can perform and recognize the high hazard situations and offer cautions to drivers. The signal phase and timing (SPAT) data are the traffic flag framework to pass data to the vehicle in arrangement to convey dynamic wellbeing warnings and cautioning to drivers [5].

Vehicular to infrastructure systems contain the parts like Vehicle on Board Unit or equipment (OBU), Roadside Unit or Equipment (RSU or RSE), Safe Communication Channel, and so on. In V2I system the OBU are the vehicle side and are utilized to characterize the vehicular capacities performed in the system. The OBU is the gathering of an application processor, GPS, and interfaces to vehicle system. It additionally gives the interfaces among the vehicles, the vehicles and RSU. OBU likewise transmit status messages to other OBU. In view of its memory and communication limit the information depictions are put away. These old information's are overwritten after a timeframe, the vehicle information alongside GPS information's is assembled as an arrangement for transmission to the RSU [21]. RSU are fixed

Fig 6: Vehicular to Infrastructure

On the roadside interfaces and exchanges like petrol stations with in the range. DSRC or WAVE is radio handsets on the RSU and Interface to the V2I interchanges arrange. An inter- face supports neighborhood foundation wellbeing applications utilizing GPS. The Vehicular to Infrastructure arrange can send the private information and furthermore get information. RSU can deal with the messages sent from the vehicle (car unique hardware producer (OEM)) and got to the vehicle by need. The needs are set in OBU inside its applications and RSU. Stimulation, open and private system applications has least need. The use of V2I center around SPAT (which can facilitate the driving pace) . It is likewise

ready to misuse the efficiency with less fuel utilization while begin and quit utilizing examples to traffic light by SPAT [19].

In our system V to I is used in a smart way and implemented in intelligent public transportation systems to provide the real time transportation information. communications happen between the vehicular, stations, infrastructure etc. To communication and transmit the data in an effective manner, we use the DSRC standard protocol IEEE 802.11p which organize with basic WAVE communication stack (WCS). The information is exchanged by a fixed radio channels CCH which is explained below. There are different layers of DSRC protocol stack stated from top to bottom. Particularly PHY and MAC layer. The DSRC PHY protocol stack is defined by IEEE 802.11p amendment. It has two sublayers (PMD) physical medium dependent sublayer and Physical layer convergence procedure (PLCP) sublayer. It also utilizes the OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing Technique) based on 802.11a amendment. The mapping between the PHY layer, MAC layer and the OFDM symbol is defined by PLCP. The amendment of IEEE 802.11p MAC layer reduce the overhead and is described by WAVE mode which solve the time-consuming issue of MAC operations. WBSS (Wave Basic service set) are formed by a station on demand for transmission, this gives a low overhead of WBSS setup. BSSID supports signaling for upper layer protocols for all vehicular transmission. To access DS (Distributed Service), A known BSSID should be used for radio communication within the context of WAVE BSS which is needed to send data frames [31] [12].

The data packet for our system is framed by using DSRC IEEE 802.11 p protocol stack. The (PPDU) procedure protocol data unit format of the above protocol stack consists of PLCP (physical layer convergence procedure) header, PLCP preamble, pad bits and also consists of Physical layer service data unit (PSDU). The above unit also has MAC header, frame check sequence (FCS field) and the values are given with the time duration [26]. An illustration of data format is given in the Figure 7.

Fig 7: IEEE 802.11p Frame Format

Using this IEEE 802.11p data format, our data described in the section III can be transmitted through the data field of the above frame format.

A. Vehicular to Vehicular communication

A vehicle can go about as an interface between one vehicle to other vehicle utilizing dynamic remote trade of information as shown in the Figure 6. The information's are imparted between vehicles by remote system. Vehicles trade data like speed, area and assets among them. V2V communication can be utilized for exchanging crisis messages, increasing GPS accuracy and trading related information. V2V correspondence can be more compelling in sharing the messages than the current (OEM) automotive original equipment manufacturer for sending and receiving messages. This innovation supports by creating a worldwide 360-degree attention to encompassing intimidation and vicinity. To control the accident or dangers in the vehicle communication the correct vehicle software or safety application can utilize messages from the close by vehicles. This innovation likewise gives administration like visual, material and capable of being heard cautions to caution drivers, so that drivers can dodge crashes. These V2V communication can recognize a risk which covers traffic, landscape or climate. The radars, sensors and cameras are utilized to recognize and transmit the messages [5].

The communication between the vehicles happens by utilizing gadget called (DSRC) Dedicated Short range correspondence. It is a wireless communication device which works in the 5.9GHz band with a transfer speed of 75MHz which is doled out for the vehicular communication. The scope of these gadgets might be around 1000m. DSRC is also communicated with road infrastructure as referenced before. To convey the street signs and hubs are introduced by roadside.

I. Hybrid Transportation Tracking System

Public transportation medium has its own vehicles, operations and infrastructure. Nowadays these transportation networks are becoming smart day by day using various techniques and made easy to communicate by passing the information in the network. Note that the term vehicles in our context stands for public transport vehicles. To make this smart hybrid public transportation system smart, tracking system is introduced.

A. System design

A public transportation system consists of multiple transport medium (say f) where each medium has a fixed number of vehicles. In order to identify such elements in the transportation system, we begin with a component categorization across transport medium and vehicles in the network. We make a precise categorization on the transportation system to adapt the hybrid nature.

We let denote $\{M_i\}^f$ be the set of f transport mediums in the network. For $i \in [n]$, let n_i be the number of vehicles in the medium M_i . For $i \in [f]$ and $j \in [n_i]$, we let denote $H_{i,j}$ be the j -th vehicle runs on the i -th medium. Each vehicle $H_{i,j}$ is uniquely associated with a source $s_{i,j}$, destination $t_{i,j}$ and an operating path $R_{i,j}$. The path $R_{i,j}$ is a sequence of

ordered stations in the network. That is, $R_{i,j} = \{r^1_{i,j}, r^2_{i,j}, \dots, r^{h_{i,j}}_{i,j}\}$ Where $h_{i,j}$ is length of the path $R_{i,j}$ is length of the path $R_{i,j}$. Observe that $r^1_{i,j} = s_{i,j}$ and $r^{h_{i,j}}_{i,j} = t_{i,j}$.

We use some graph theoretic notations to denote the system. Let $G = (V, E)$ be the transportation network that we are interested to setup smart transportation. Given a public transportation network with multiple types of transport mediums,

we design the system as follows. Let M_1, M_2, \dots, M_l be the set of all transport medium in G for some $l \geq 1$. We assume that the system is feasible. Every node in the network is a station for some vehicle. That is

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \bigcup_{j=1}^n \bigcup_{k=1}^f r^k_{i,j} = V.$$

Further, every edge (or link) is associated in the traveling path of some vehicle. That is,

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \bigcup_{j=1}^n \bigcup_{k=1}^f r^k_{i,j} r^{k+1}_{i,j} = E.$$

Let us ponder the above network Figure 8. The network is presented for $f = 3$. Here we use blue color, green and red colors for each medium. The nodes on the network are representing stations. The stations denoted in square are either source or destination terminal for some vehicle. To make presentation clear, consider a one single medium with green color which is 2nd medium as shown in the Figure 9. It has 3 different paths and four terminal nodes. As we mentioned above, a traveling path of a vehicle is a sequence of ordered nodes in the network. Assume that the vertices are ordered

Fig 8: A transportation network with three mediums represented in blue, green and red, respectively

Fig 9: Green medium of the transport network given in Figure 8

From p_1 to p_{21} as shown in Figure 8. The nodes p_1 to p_7 represent the path P_1 . Similarly, the nodes p_7 to p_{15} and p_{15} to p_{21} represent the paths P_2 and P_3 respectively. We used to denote the vehicles ran in the network with $H_{2,j}$ for $1 \leq j \leq 3$, since the medium is numbered by 2. Consider the vehicle $H_{2,1}$. As we stated above, a vehicle is associated a triple that contains source, destination and traveling path. In this network, we have $s_{2,1} = p_1$, $t_{2,1} = p_7$, $R_{2,1} = P_1$ and $h_{2,1} = 7$. For $k \in [h_{2,1}]$, $r^k = p_k$.

Now we are ready to demonstrate the architecture of the system. Speaking at high level, our system has a hybrid nature that contains vehicles, stations, sensors, receivers, cloud, display and tracking services. our system consists set of vehicles and set of stations in all the medium. Each and every station has sensors, receivers which can communicate, receive data from the vehicles onboard unit and transmit to intermediate level communicator (RSU). All the vehicles in our system have been installed with DSRC onboard unit, which will send the data to the Roadside sensors, RSU and also to the other onboard unit. Our system architecture is connected with a vehicular cloud network where RSU can store and update all the data's received from the sensors and onboard unit. Finally, all this information will be frequently updated, tracked and displayed in all the stopping points using display and tracking services. Detailed explanation about all these services are given in the Figure 10.

Fig 10: Architecture Diagram

B. DSRC on Vehicle

Dedicated short range communication (DSRC) is a low cost, short range wireless communication technology consists of band 5.925GHz range of radio frequency spectrum allocated by US federal communication commission to improve the communication in the transportation system. DSRC allows to communicate in both vehicle to vehicle or vehicle to infrastructure network [31]. It communicates using transponders such as Onboard units and RSU. Here vehicles communicate with each other using Onboard units.

DSRC is also a low-cost short-range band capable of delivering 27 Mbps data rate. DSRC is the cellular communication services envisioned to support communication and very high data transfer in Vehicular-to-Vehicular channels and vehicular to Infrastructure channels. This communication distance is maximum up to 300 meters under the default transmitting power and also the latency time is maximum up to 150 milliseconds for 4096-bit package transmission [30].

In our hybrid transportation tracking system, all the vehicles and stations are installed with DSRC on-board units. On-board units are smart communication device designed for the standardized communication with DSRC microwave link operating at 5.8 GHz. This units are in-vehicle device which can be installed on vehicles to provide the application run-time environment and communication interfaces.

These on-board units are the transceiver of DSRC, which is mounted in or on a vehicle. it is used to transmit or receive data on one or more radio frequency channels when a vehicle is either mobile or immobile [7] [31]. Since DSRC operates on 5.9 GHz frequency band, on-board unit are mounted on each vehicle that has transceivers and transponders to communicate with roadside unit or with other on-board unit vehicles and also road side sensors.

The DSRC technology is used to acquire the necessary information about the vehicle. Information about the vehicle can also be broadcasted to other vehicles which are in the frequency range if needed [31].

Thus, whenever the vehicle passes a station, it communicates the necessary information to the receiver using on-board device installed in it. On-board unit exchanges information to other on-board unit, RSU and road-side sensors using the fixed radio channels CCH. The channel spectrum of DSRC is having 5.9 GHz frequency band. This spectrum is divided into seven 10 MHz channels with each channels separated as 5 MHz guard band at low level end.

The pairs of 10 MHz channels can be formed into 20 MHz channels. These channel separation and the frequency band are shown in the Figure 11. It consists of service channels and control channels. All these channels are used to communicate in the network, each channel uses specific rules based on the application type for communication [31] [12].

Fig 11: IEEE 802.11p channel frequency band

C. Sensors on Stations

In order to access the location of vehicles, each vehicle has to update the information of passing a station on the traveling path to the cloud repository. In our system, we are not using the GPS technology to access the location[32].

Though we are using DSRC technology, an alternate to the GPS to track the vehicles through the updates to the receiver/sensor on each station. A vehicle can communicate to the receiver on a station. So, we need to install RSU on each station to get information from the vehicles passing through it.

It requires a major investment for purchase, install and maintain the RSU on each station. To utilize the system in a cost-effective manner, here we use only reduced number of roadside units for communication and data transmission [13] [8].

Hence in our system for V2I communication that is communication between vehicle onboard unit and infrastructure, we use roadside wireless sensors and the networking technology, which will be the appropriate solution for cost effective communication [33].

The devices installed on each station is an IoT integrated DSRC transceiver. The role of the device is as follows:

- 1) To receive the information from vehicle on-board units and acknowledge them.
- 2) Pass the information to nearest RSU located.

Further, each station is assigned a unique RSU which is installed widely on the network. An RSU is a central information transmitting point, where the information gathered from the stations is communicated to cloud through it. Meanwhile, the sensors on the stations act as smart transceiver. More precisely, the sensor can handle multiple receiving and acknowledging operations[34].

With this capability, we claim that the probability of error is very less and negligible on practice. Also, the sensors are acting as transmitter to transmit the information gathered from vehicle on-board unit to the allocated RSU Figure 12.

The communication to the roadside units is given in fig.

Fig 12: DSRC technology with RSU installation

D. Cloud Storage in Hybrid Transportation

We use cloud storage to monitor the transportation system. We prefer vehicular cloud storage as a service with all the other services for data storage. The updates made at stations to report the status of vehicle are collected and accumulated at the cloud server [35]. These data are passed by several transceivers those are in stations and RSUs.

For the tracking and servicing purpose, we use the cloud storage system as a centralized database server. We have designed three tables in the server among them one is static table and the rest are dynamic tables [36]. We used to call the tables are *meta transport table* (MTT), *dynamic update table* (DUT) and *report and archive table* (RAT).

The MTT is a static table which contains the set of all vehicle and their traveling path. The MTT is defined with two columns, say (*V ID*) and (*path*). The roll and usage of the column are as follows:

- (*V ID*): An unique identity that is used to identify the vehicle (act as primary key to find the vehicle).
- (*path*): A list of ID of the stations in which the vehicle travels. This value of similar to the *R* value given in the system design.

This table is called meta table since the entries are made when there are some changes in the route of the vehicles.

The DUT is a dynamic table which contains the latest status of the vehicles. The DUT is defined with the following columns:

(V ID, trip, status, time, live Station, reporting Status)

The roll and usage of the column are as follows:

- (*V ID*): An unique identity that is used to identify the vehicle.
- (*trip*): Trip number of the vehicle. Used when multiple vehicles operating in the same ID. Otherwise set to null. If the trip is not null, then the combined fields (*V ID*, *trip*) is used as primary key to find the vehicle. Otherwise, (*V ID*) is sufficient to find a vehicle.
- (*status*): Current status of the vehicle which is uniquely identified by the combined fields (*V ID*, *trip*). The possible value of the fields is "running" and "repair". If the vehicle is updating a arrival or departure then the field is set to "running", otherwise "repair". If the vehicle is not started from the source, then the (*status*) is marked as "yet - to - start".
- (*time*): Reporting time of the vehicle. This value is obtained from the update operations.
- (*liveStation*): Identity of the station in which the vehicle is reported the arrival, departure or repair. In case of arrival or departure, the *liveStation* is reporting station ID. If the reporting is the "repair", then the *liveStation* value is the last station of the vehicle in which it successfully reported.
- (*reportingStatus*): This value is an extension of the field (*status*). If the (*status*) is "yet-to-start", then the (*reportingStatus*) is 0 (not started). If the (*status*) is "running", then the (*reportingStatus*) is either 1 (arrival) or 2 (departure). If the (*status*) is "repair", then the (*reportingStatus*) is 3 (repair).

This table rows are dynamically changed when an update of a vehicle is sent through a station and RSU to the cloud server. The RAT is used for the archive and log purpose. Running history of each vehicle is stored the RAT

The RAT is defined with the following columns:

(*V ID*, *trip*, *SID*, *time*, *status*).

The roll and usage of the columns are given as follows:

- (*V ID*): An unique identity that is used to identify the vehicle.
- (*trip*): Trip number of the vehicle. Used when multiple vehicles operating in the same ID. Otherwise set to null.
- (*SID*): An unique identity of a station. We have rows for each station in which the vehicle (*V ID*) travels along the (*path*) described in the MTT.
- (*time*): Time of reporting by the vehicle (*V ID*) at station (*SID*).
- (*status*): Status of reporting by the vehicle (*V ID*) at station (*SID*). The status of reporting is either 1 (arrival), 2 (departure) or 3 (repair). If the (*status*) is 3, then the station (*SID*) is the last station to be updated.

E. Communication Protocols

Dedicated Short Range Communication system has two-way wireless communication protocols that combines with IEEE 802.11, 1609.x standards, SAE J2735, and SAE J2945[1]. We list the different types of communication happen between vehicles, stations, RSUs and cloud server.

There are four types of update operations used in our system.

UPDATE-I(A): Performed when a vehicle communicate to a station to report the arrival. The operation is initiated by the vehicle and acknowledged by the reporting station. Let X be a vehicle arriving the station S at time t . Let r be the trip number of the vehicle X . The DSRC on-board unit in the vehicle sends an information to the DSRC receiver at the station S .

The information contains

$$(X.ID, r, S.ID, t, type = 1).$$

The fifth field in the information ($type$) is used to identify the arrival/departure of the vehicle to the station.

UPDATE-I(B): Performed when a vehicle communicates to a station to report the departure. This update is similar to UPDATE-I(A) except the $type$ value in the set to 2. That is the information is as follows:

$$(X.ID, r, S.ID, t, type = 2)$$

vehicle X reports the departure to the station S at time t during the trip r .

UPDATE-I(C): Performed when a vehicle communicates to a station to report a repair request of another vehicle. Let X be a vehicle reported and departed from a station S_1 on the trip r . Let S_2 be the next station to be arrived by the vehicle

X . Due to some accidental situation, the vehicle is stopped between the stations S_1 and S_2 . An information is send to the vehicle passing through it. The information contains

$$(X.ID, r, S_1.ID, t_1, t_2, type = 3)$$

where t_1 and t_2 are the time of accident and the current time. The information is passed by another vehicle X^1 that is passing through X and reporting to the next station of X^1 .

UPDATE-II: Performed to report the UPDATE-I information (both (A), (B) and (C) updates) to the RSU by a station. The information communicated to the RSU contains the following:

$$(X.ID, r, S.ID, t_1, t_2, type)$$

where the vehicle X reported to S at time t_2 . The type field determines the type of reporting (arrival, departure or accident). If it is an accident report, then the time of accident is determined by the field t_1 .

UPDATE-III: Performed to update the arrival, departure or repair of a vehicle on or after a station by the RSU to the cloud server (database). During this update operation, an update information that contains

$$(X.ID, r, S.ID, t_1, t_2, type)$$

is send to cloud server and the information make an entry to the dynamic table in the cloud server. During the operation, the server finds an entry with a unique key $(X.ID, r)$.

F. Tracking and Services

Smart transportation systems offer the vehicle tracking facility to the users. The vehicle tracking is facilitated due to the monitoring services and smart nature. In our system we provide couple of station-based vehicle tracking services. Let S be a station.

- 1) SERVICE-I: On inputting a vehicle X , users can find the latest running location and running status of the vehicle X . Note that the station S is on the running path of the vehicle X .
- 2) SERVICE-II: On inputting a destination station S^1 , users can find the running location, status and expected arrival times of the upcoming vehicles that will operate to S^1

Algorithm 1: Dynamic table update by the UPDATE- III operation

Data: An update information

$$(X.ID, r, S.ID, t_1, t_2, type)$$

Result: Updates the dynamic table

Let w be the row corresponding to the key $(X.ID, r)$;

if $type$ is 3 **then**

Set $w.status = \text{"repair"}^{11}$; Set $w.time = t_1$;

else

Set $W.status = \text{"running"}^{11}$; Set $W.liveStation = S.ID$; Set $w.time = t_1$;

Set $w.reportingStatus = type$;

end

Algorithm 2: Request handling of SERVICE-I

Data: Vehicle route-number X , station S and time t

Result: $T = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_c\}$.

Let $R = \text{Query the DUT table with } VID = X.ID \text{ and}$

status = running and *liveStation < S.ID* to find

trip;

if *R* is non-empty **then**

Create a list *T* with entries in *R*;

else

Let r^1 be the next *trip* value of the vehicle to be started from the source station;

Set $T = \{r^1\}$

End

return *T*;

to *S*. Note that the stations *S* and S^1 has direct vehicle service.

The services are offered to the users through a digital display with compatible input/output mechanism. This ensures that every station must have a monitoring display facility. However, these kinds of devices are mandatory when we facilitate the station-based vehicle tracking services.

We now describe the first service, on inputting a vehicle *X*, the system displays the information of all the vehicle which are operating with route-number as *X* and operating at current time. There can be multiple vehicles with similar route-number can be operated. However, there will be a unique identity available for each vehicle (as discussed in previous section). Let *SID* be the current station, *X* be the queried vehicle route-number and *t* be the current time, then (SID, X, t) is the request raised by the users through the display device. We need to find all the vehicles which are operating with route- number *X*. Also, the vehicles should be running at the moment between the source and the station *S* or about to start from the source.

Let us define $T = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_c\}$ for some $c \geq 0$

be the set of trips ids of the vehicles operating with route-number as *X* and operating between the source station and

S. Let r^1 be the trip id of the vehicle which is the upcoming vehicle to start the trip from the source station. The set *T* can be computed by querying the DUT table. When $c = 0$, that is no vehicle are operating between the source station to *S*, then the vehicle with trip id as r^1 will be displayed since it will be the first vehicle to reach the station *S*. We will display the following information in ordered list fashion. For each trip $r \in T$, the latest *liveStation*, *status* and update *time* will be displayed in the display in a list order.

Similarly, SERVICE-II is described as follows. Let S^1 be the target station inputted by an user. First, we need to find the availability of direct vehicle service from the station *S* to S^1 . This can be found by query the MTT table. If it exists,

find set of all the vehicle route-numbers such that the vehicles are operated through S and S^1 . Let $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_z\}$ be the set of all vehicle route-numbers as described above. For each vehicle route-number $d \in D$, call the Algorithm 2, with the parameter (d, S, t) where t is current time. For each such call to the Algorithm 2, returns a set of upcoming trips on its respective vehicle route-number. Accumulate the results, order them according to the closest *liveStation* as a list and display it to the user. An illustration of Display Service to the user Figure 13

Fig 13: Display Service

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the performance of the proposed hybrid transportation tracking system is evaluated. The results are analyzed in the following section.

A. Performance Analysis

The experimental results are described in this section. The experiments compare different communication platforms, such as DSRC, Long Term Evolution (LTE), Wireless Fidelity (WIFI), and Third Generation (3G) with the proposed hybrid transportation tracking system. Here, the data are processed to analyze the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), Packet Loss Ratio (PLR), End-to-End Delay, Throughput, Process Time, Response Time, Waiting Time, Execution Time, and Turn Around Time (TAT) as a function of the number of vehicles.

Table 1: performance comparison of the proposed hybrid system based on PDR

No of Vehicles	500	400	300	200	100
3G	76	73	70	67	63
WIFI	73	70	68	65	63.45
LTE	81	80	77	76	73
DSRC	83.9	88	87	85	83.3

Table 1 analysis the effectiveness of the proposed scheme by comparing its PDR output using different communication platforms. The packet delivery ratio is the ratio of the number of packets received at the destination to the number of packets sent from the source. The performance is better when the packet delivery ratio is high. In this context, the PDR increases as the number of vehicles range from 100 to 500. On analysing table 1, the proposed model attains higher values of PDR using DSRC, which is 10.3% than using the 3G, WIFI, and LTE methods. Hence, the results of this experiment show that DSRC proffers better performance than the other platforms.

Figure 14: PLR Vs Number of Vehicles

Figure 7 analyses the PLR of the proposed method. The reliability of a communication network path is expressed by the packet loss rate. This metric is equal to the ratio of packets not received to the packets sent. For the number of 100 to 200 nodes, the PLR of the proposed method using DSRC is increased from 11 to 13, whereas the PLR using LTE, WIFI, and 3G methods is increased from 16 to 23, 32 to 34, and 37 to 38. Hence, the analysis showed that the performance of the proposed method with DSRC is better than the other communication methods.

Table 2: Performance analysis with respect to Throughput

No of Vehicles	100	200	300	400	500
DSRC	1756	2305	2855	3447	3752
LTE	1458	1846	2392	2902	3185
WIFI	1105	1427	1863	2308	2641
3G	942	1137	1484	1764	2274

Table 2 illustrates the amount of data transmitted successfully from one place to another in a given time period. For a maximum of 100 vehicles, the throughput of the proposed method with DSRC is 298 times higher than the LTE technique. Accordingly, compared to WIFI and 3G techniques, the proposed method attains better throughput while using DSRC. For the remaining number of vehicles also, the DSRC method results in a higher

throughput value. Therefore, the analysis delivered that the proposed method with the DSRC scheme has better performance for an increasing number of vehicles.

Figure 15: End-to-End delay analysis

End-to-End delay of the proposed hybrid transportation tracking system is analysed in figure 15. End-to-end delay refers to the time taken for a packet to be transmitted across a network from source to destination. The maximum end-to-end delay signifies the low processing ability of the system. In this regard, the end-to-end delay of the proposed method is lower for DSRC, which varied as 483 ms for 100 nodes, 804 ms for 200 nodes, 1484 ms for 300 nodes, 2297 ms for 400 nodes, and 3351 ms for 500 nodes. Compared to the LTE, WIFI, and 3G methods, the proposed method using DSRC took much lesser time for packet transmission. From this analysis, it is clear that the proposed method with DSRC is more efficient than the other techniques.

Table 3: Performance Analysis based on TAT

No of Vehicles	100	200	300	400	500
3G	253	418	612	796	1012
WIFI	204	366	524	713	904
LTE	174	341	466	611	852
DSRC	154	305	408	533	736

Table 3 shows the performance of the proposed method in terms of TAT. TAT is the amount of time taken to complete a process or fulfil a request. As TAT represents the speed of the execution process, it should be lower for better performance of the system. From table 3, the TAT taken by the proposed method using LTE, WIFI, and 3G for 500 vehicles is 72 ms, 180 ms, and 277 ms higher than using DSRC. The time taken by DSRC for the proposed method is increased as the number of vehicles increases but the increasing level of the DSRC is not exceeded the LTE, WIFI, and 3G techniques. From this analysis, DSRC's efficiency for the proposed model is proved.

Figure 16: Response Time Vs Number of Vehicles

Figure 10 evinces the performance of the proposed methods in terms of response time. It represents the actual time spent working on a task. For the maximum number of vehicles, the response time taken by the proposed method is 5672 for DSRC, 6168 ms for LTE, 6593 ms for WIFI, and 6854 ms for 3G. From this analysis, the LTE, WIFI, and 3G techniques have lower response times compared to the proposed method with DSRC. The analysis concludes that the proposed method using DSRC is superior to other methods.

Figure 17: Execution Time Vs Number of Vehicles

Figure 17 shows the execution time of the proposed method while using DSRC, LTE, WIFI, and 3G communication platforms. From figure 17, it is observed that the time taken by the proposed method for DSRC is much lesser than other techniques. When a minimum number of vehicles is 100, the execution time of the proposed method is 367 ms using DSRC, 447 ms using LTE, 531 ms using WIFI, and 627 ms using 3G. Hence the analysis concludes that the performance of the proposed method is far better when using DSRC than the other techniques.

Figure 18: Process Time Vs Number of Vehicles

The process time of the proposed method is analysed in above figure 18 using DSRC, LTE, WIFI, and 3G techniques. From the graph, it can be stated that the proposed method using DSRC tends to obtain the process time ranging from 4965 ms to 16957 ms for the vehicles ranging between 100 and 500. But, the methodology with LTE, WIFI, and 3G methods tends to achieve process time ranging from 5347 ms to 25227 ms, which illustrates that the proposed work is better when using DSRC as the communication platform

Figure 19: Waiting time Vs Number of Vehicles

The waiting time of the proposed method is depicted in above figure 19. As the Waiting time increases, the performance of the network reduces. According to that, the proposed method with DSRC tends to obtain a waiting time ranging from 172 ms to 611 ms, whereas the existing methodology tends to achieve an overall waiting time ranging from

219 ms to 987 ms, which is relatively high as compared to the DSRC method. Thus, the results conclude that the proposed method can choose DSRC as the main communication platform to transmit the data to the destination source without any loss of data.

4. EXPERIMENTAL CHALLENGES

In this section we discuss the challenges and issues in experiment the system. Primary aspects of the experiment are to evaluate the quality and/or advancement compare to the existing system. So, we identify set of systems that can be compared to our system.

A. National train enquiry system in India

Indian railways (IR) is one of the biggest rail network in the world. The tracking and maintenance system in the IR involves high man power and machines. Specific to the tracking service, nation train enquiry system (NTES) takes care of it. The NTES is maintained by a technical organization under Ministry of Railways named *center for railways information systems* (CRIS).

The NTES is a cloud-based information management system developed to maintain the arrival and departure records of the trains. For each train during the travel at each station in which the train passing through, the arrival and departure time is updated by the staffs on each day of the travel. Whenever a train crosses (both arrival and departure) a station, the time is updated by the station staffs to the information system. This involves a huge number of man power and machinery.

The information recorded by the staff and the system delay together cause a significant delay in the system to pass the information at different level. Sometimes, the information is not recorded at some stations due to lack of work at the station staffs. This lead to the information latency in the system.

B. Our system to serve NTES

Our system is an alternative to the huge man power involved in the NTES. Also, our system overcomes few inadequate information services. We proposed a unmanned automated signaling/communication using DSRC. The cost of man-power versus the cost of machinery involved in our system for the vehicle tracking is a better trade of when the number of vehicle and the number of stations is large in count. Especially, large systems like IR (20000+ rail services and 8000+ stations), our system will perform better than the existing one.

Here we demonstrate the system structure of the smart transportation to the IR. Execution of the system is demon- strated in the previous section. Recall that, each train (an active service) is treated as a vehicle with unique identity installed a DSRC on-board unit.

Each station will act as a road side sensor with necessary signal receiving capability. By the described protocols and services, the train tracking (arrival and departure) can be automated with highly reliable DSRC technology integrated with vehicular cloud.

The train arrival and departure time has been updated to the cloud system with admissible delay (due to signaling and communication delay). This will provide an improved quality of tracking service to the large number of users.

C. Experiments on DSRC

Here we list the set of experimental works done related to DSRC. We are sophisticated to point these experiments to show evidence to address the issues and challenges in the implementation. DSRC communication standard which we use in our transportation system is DSRC IEEE 802.11p protocol standard.

Patil et al. [22] showed that the IEEE standard 802.11p used in DSRC performs better than IEEE standard 802.11a across different parameters like delivery ratio and etc., Thus, the standard used in DSRC is highly reliable. Tseng et al. [28] implemented a real-time on-road testing of the WAVE/DSRC payment system for vehicular communication.

Dow et al. [6] proposed the DSRC based warning and rapid notification of traffic information in vehicular system. This system is capable of detecting road hazard and transmitting traffic information to the internet, the information is passed through CAN packet format. Choi et al. [4] designed an architecture to improve the rail road crossing safety, vehicle to rail road characterization and DSRC performance results at rail road crossing at urban and suburban environments.

Authors implemented Field testing to analyse the feasibility of providing warning signals using DSRC communication system. Hussain et al. [10] established the relative lane and position of surrounding vehicles in real time. The authors used DSRC based V-TO-V communication and standard GPS receivers, This DSRC equipped vehicle transmits and receives Basic Safety messages (BSM) every 100msec among neighboring vehicles.

The calculation based on the position information is given in terms of longitude and latitude. Field tests were performed in the variety of curved sections. The relative position of the surrounding vehicles in terms of which is trailing ahead or behind can be identified without any errors within few meters.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a novel design for smart transportation using vehicular cloud. Our design involves GPS-less tracking system which uses DSRC communication devices. The designed system incorporates DSRC based on IEEE 802.11p standard. On the basis of the experiments and data analysis, we found that the DSRC-based communication performs better and has lesser communication latency.

Also, this system can be applied to any transportation model such as road, train and etc., by applying this proposed system, tracking system proposed in the IR can be improved. Furthermore, the proposed system simplifies the process of communication and roles of RSU that effectively reducing cost and resources. We will be developing and evaluating novel design for smart transportation using vehicular cloud in the near future.

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